

MetaPlantCode: Communication Strategy

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Why – Vision:

To make the expertise gained by the members of MetaPlantCode available to the scientific public to provide a starting point for new researchers and promote innovation in the field of metabarcoding.

Where – Goals:

The products from the MetaPlantCode project will be invaluable to the field of plant metabarcoding and the ecological inquiry and biomonitoring potential the method provides. We seek to raise awareness of our project to foster collaboration and engagement across various disciplines to enhance our results by gaining insight into the needs of researchers worldwide.

How – Strategy:

- **Brand Recognition:** We aim to create MetaPlantCode as a common term within the eDNA and plant research communities by performing targeted outreach and engagement strategies to raise awareness to the valuable resources we will provide.
- **Alignment with Values:** We will ensure that all publications, protocols, and databases produced by individuals and teams within the MetaPlantCode project align with FAIR data standards. We will prominently include MetaPlantCode members and the project funders in all outreach activities and publications to establish a key contact and enhance recognition.
- **Adaptability:** Design MetaPlantCode output to be adaptable and updateable, allowing researchers to customize their research design while upholding FAIR research principles. This will enable innovation and promote comparability and collaboration across projects worldwide.
- **Performance Evaluation:** The resources provided by MetaPlantCode will serve as a framework for evaluating performance of alternate field, laboratory, and analytical methods.

What – Operational Concept

- **For all FOR ALL WRITTEN MATERIALS**, including papers published in scientific journals and policy briefs, indicate the following sentences: This research was

funded by Biodiversa+, the European Biodiversity Partnership, in the context of the MetaPlantCode project under the 2022-2023 BiodivMon joint call. It was co-funded by the European Commission (GA No. 101052342) and the following funding organisations: [Funding organisation 1], [Funding organisation 2], [Funding organisation 3], and [Funding organisation 4].

- **IN ANY VISUAL** (PowerPoint, poster, social media visual, video, project's website...) use the Biodiversa+ logo (see the guidelines) & EU emblem, as well as the logos of the relevant funding organizations

Doing – Realization:

- **Content Creation:** We will publish scientific manuscripts and create a webpage with links to usable protocols for field, lab, and bioinformatics protocols for nearly all areas of plant metabarcoding. This will also serve to provide contact people for further inquiries for interested researchers worldwide.
- **Campaign management:** Identifying target audience. Actions taken to interact with target audiences, including meetings, presentations, and feedback sessions to bring presence to the MetaPlantCode project and broaden the reach and objectives of MetaPlantCode.
- **Channel Selection:** Choosing the appropriate platforms (e.g., social media, email, websites) to disseminate messages effectively.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Implementing systems (e.g. online survey) to track the effectiveness of communication efforts, assessing reach and impact, and making adjustments as needed
- **Training and Development:** Providing training and secondments.
- **Partnerships and Collaborations:** Collaborate with other organizations or stakeholders to increase outreach and scale up continuity efforts (e.g. GBIF, ELIXIR and others).

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